

CORONAVIRUS & COVID-19

What is coronavirus:

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses known to cause more serious diseases from the common cold, such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS).

Coronaviruses were identified in the mid-1960s.

Sars-Corona Virus (SARS-CoV) is a coronavirus that was first seen in China in February 2003 and causes severe acute respiratory failure. As the **largest** known **RNA viruses** (because coronaviruses have the largest genome of RNA viruses), CoVs are further divided into four types: alphacoronavirus (α -CoV), betacoronavirus (β -CoV), gammacoronavirus (γ -CoV), and deltacoronavirus (δ -CoV); the first two only infect mammals, including bats, pigs, cats and humans. Gammacoronavirus mostly infects birds and Deltacoronavirus can infect both birds and mammals. This novel coronavirus is now the seventh member of the Coronaviridae, which is known to infect humans. All Coronaviruses belong to a genus. All of these genera are in the **Coronaviridae** family, making up one of the two subfamilies. Coronavirus, Nidovirales, which causes infections mainly in the respiratory and gastrointestinal tract, belongs to the Orthocoronavirinae subfamily, respectively in the Coronaviridae family. Previously, with serological analysis, the differences in the Coronavirus species used were understood and the Coronaviridae family was examined by dividing it into 4 antigenic groups. But then, by examining the monoclonal antibody analysis and nucleotide sequences in the species and division groups, the classification was reduced to 3 antigenic groups. Viruses in the coronavirus family have only slight differences in their genomes, with only five nucleotide differences between the three of the viruses. Regardless of the structure of the protein chains, the same results in the same groups showed that this classification is more accurate. Coronaviruses responsible for 30% of upper respiratory tract diseases in humans are included in group 1 (HCoV-229E) and group 2 (HCoV-OC43). TGEV (Porcine transmissible gastroenteritis virus), FCV (Feline coronavirus), CCV (Canine coronavirus) in group 1 and all members of group 2 are genetically very close to each other. IBV, the only member of the 3rd group, is not different from other coronaviruses, but it shows variations within its species. Group 1 and group 2 coronaviruses include mammalian viruses.

COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2)

The epidemic, which caused the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare an international public health emergency and is currently ongoing, called 2019-nCoV in the days it started, then COVID-19 by the official decision of WHO, has been on the agenda of the world since the last days of December 2019. However, with the emergence of the COVID-19 virus, many uncertainties remain regarding some epidemiological, seroepidemiological (related to the identification of antibodies in the population), clinical and virological characteristics of the virus and related disease.

COVID-19 name expansion; While the 'Co' corona, 'Vi' virus and 'D' disease mean, '19' indicates the year since the epidemic was first identified in 2019.

At the end of 2019, COVID-19 appeared in several local hospitals in Wuhan, Hubei Province of China. Based on clinical findings, blood tests and chest radiographs, this disease was diagnosed with viral pneumonia by clinicians.

- With an explosion of confirmed cases, WHO declared this outbreak an international alarming public health emergency (PHEIC) on January 30, 2020.

(This article has been prepared from different sources. Also comments have been added.) This paper is about the past traces of Corona Viruses and the current status of COVID-19. Detailed information about the epidemiology of the Corona virus is included. This paper is extensive however it consists of important information.

This new type of coronavirus; it is known to cause a variety of symptoms such as **pneumonia**, fever, respiratory distress and lung infection. These viruses are common in animals worldwide but very few cases are known to affect humans.

The new coronavirus (nCoV) is a **strain** that hasn't been seen in humans before. Although the coronavirus that caused the epidemic was not initially familiar, it is likely that many people have actually encountered milder types of this virus before. Because four strains of this virus are responsible for about a fifth of common cold cases. Coronaviruses are part of a large family of viruses that can be found in both humans and animals. Some can infect humans and cause a common cold or very serious illnesses such as MERS (Middle Eastern respiratory syndrome) and SARS (severe acute respiratory syndrome).

Coronaviruses are **zoonotic**, transmitted between animals and humans. Research in this area shows that the SARS-CoV virus is transmitted from the African civet cat and the MERS-CoV virus from the arabian camel. Some types of coronavirus known to circulate among animals have never been transmitted to humans.

SARS-CoV-2 is a coronavirus strain first detected in Wuhan, China's Hubei region. Based on clinical findings, blood tests and chest radiographs, this disease was diagnosed with viral pneumonia by clinicians.

So what is pneumonia:

Pneumonia is a type of chest infection commonly known as pneumonia. It affects the alveoli in the lungs. When pneumonia occurs, these air sacs become inflamed and fill with fluid. Because pneumonia; it is an inflammation of the lung tissue caused by bacteria, viruses, fungi and other microorganisms. Apart from these factors, factors such as inhalation of various gases and radiotherapy can also develop pneumonia by damaging the lung tissue.

The epidemic started as a pneumonia outbreak caused by unknown factors in December 2019. On January 30, 2020; the World Health Organization (WHO) announced that this epidemic was defined as "the International Emergency Public Health Problem". WHO has temporarily determined the name of the disease that caused the current epidemic as 2019-nCoV, when it was first detected in 2019 and referring to the coronavirus family with "n" meaning "new". On February 11, 2020, WHO announced that the virus was named Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona Virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), and the disease caused by the virus was named Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19), which was identified in 2019.

Coronavirus discovery and types:

Coronaviruses were first discovered in the 1960s. Among the first viruses discovered, there are infectious bronchitis virus that appears in chickens and two types of viruses, named human coronavirus 229E and OC43, taken from the nasal cavities of human patients who show cold symptoms.

Later on;

- SARS coronavirus discovered in 2003,
- HCoV NL63 designated in 2004,
- HKU1 diagnosed in 2005,
- MERS-CoV recognized in 2012
- 2019-nCoV of Wuhan origin

Many new types of coronavirus have been discovered, including viruses like Most of these viruses cause serious respiratory infections.

Severe Acute Respiratory Failure Syndrome (SARS-CoV):

SARS was first detected as a coronavirus strain in 2003. People with the first infection were traced to Guangdong province of China in 2002, but the source of the virus is still unclear.

This virus has become an epidemic. It caused more than 8000 flu-like infections in 26 countries, and with this, nearly 800 deaths.

Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV):

MERS was first described in Saudi Arabia in 2012 in people who showed symptoms such as fever, cough, shortness of breath, and sometimes diarrhea. An animal source has not been officially confirmed for the virus, but evidence points to camels as a source of infection.

Primary reservoirs and hosts of coronaviruses:

Identifying the source and source of transmission is important to develop preventive strategies to include infection. In the case of SARS-CoV, researchers initially focused on raccoon dogs and palm musk as the most important reservoir of infection. However, only samples isolated from musk in the food market showed positive results for viral RNA detection, suggesting that musk palm could be secondary hosts. In 2001, samples were isolated from healthy people of Hongkong and the molecular assessment showed a %2,5 frequency rate of antibodies to SARS-coronavirus. These indications suggest that the SARS-coronavirus could be circulating in humans without causing an epidemic in 2003. It was later found that Rhinolophus bats have anti-SARS-CoV antibodies suggesting that bats are the source of viral replication. Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) coronavirus first appeared in Saudi Arabia in 2012. MERS-coronavirus is also related to beta-coronavirus and has camels as a zoonotic source or primary host. In a recent study, MERS-coronavirus was also detected in Pipersrellus and Perimyotis bats. Initially, a group of researchers suggested snakes were possible hosts but findings of genomic similarity between SARS-like bat viruses and the novel coronavirus suggested that bats and not snakes alone could be key reservoirs. Further analysis of homologous recombination revealed that the receptor binding spike glycoprotein of the novel coronavirus was developed from a SARS-CoV (CoVZXC21 or CoVZC45) and an as yet unknown Beta-CoV.

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The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared approximately 43 million cases of infection and approximately 1,100,000 deaths in 219 countries since the first outbreak.

Coronaviruses mutate relatively easily and can adapt to new environments; it can enter new cells and tissues and affect them.

How COVID-19 compares with other diseases:

Current estimates of the case fatality rate of COVID-19 suggest that the coronavirus is less lethal than pathogens of other large-scale epidemics such as SARS (severe acute respiratory syndrome), MERS (Middle East respiratory syndrome) and Ebola. But the infection seems to spread more easily than other diseases, including seasonal flu. *The Basic Reproductive Coefficient (R₀)* of the virus (the rate at which the infected person spreads the virus to the people around him) shows a value in the range of 2-2,5.

Like the case/fatality rate, "R₀" is a rate that can vary significantly according to location, age group and time and should be constantly revised. R₀ is calculated using models that take into account how long an infected person is contagious, likely to infect and how often they come into contact with other people.

Morphology of coronaviruses:

Coronaviruses are viruses with enveloped helical nucleocapsids, usually approximately 120nm (min[~]65 nm) in size, containing a single-stranded, positive-polarity, 26 to 32kbs long RNA (mRNA) as a nucleic material. That is, their genetic material consists of an RNA strand and each viral particle is wrapped in a protein envelope. In addition, they are viruses with the largest genome of all RNA viruses. All viruses follow basically the same path when infecting their hosts. The virus that invades a cell copies itself using some components of that cell and then the copies infect other cells. However, RNA viruses have a different feature. These viruses cannot correct errors that occur during replication because they do not have the error correction mechanisms that cells typically use to copy DNA in the process of RNA replication. However, coronaviruses are the longest genome of RNA viruses with 30,000 bases. These pathogens, which lack the ability to correct errors during replication, are more likely to make mistakes as the amount of base they copy increases. Therefore, each error brings with it a new mutation. Some of these mutations can also give the virus new features, such as the ability to infect new cell types, or even new species. The helix formed by the nucleocapsid is covered by the capsid and surrounded by an envelope outside it. At least three structural proteins are associated with the viral envelope: While the membrane protein and the envelope protein are found in the virus structure, the hedgehog mediates the entry of the virus into cells. Within the structural proteins, thorns create protrusions on the surface of the virus and give the virus a crown appearance (which means corona in Latin). In addition to mediating the entry of the virus into the cell, the spines determine the tissue the virus will enter with the range of the cell to which it will enter, but it also makes it difficult for the cell to produce immune responses. There are peplomers reaching 20 nm in length on the envelope. These peplomers allow the virus to have a crown appearance.

COVID-19 VS OTHER DISEASES

Estimates suggest the COVID-19 coronavirus is less deadly than the related illnesses SARS or MERS, but more infectious (R₀) than seasonal influenza.

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One of the surface proteins on the envelope is the Spike (S) protein, about 20nm long, with high glycosylation. Because of their length, this S Glycoprotein is the outermost part of the virion. The S Glycoprotein allows the virus to attach to the specific cell and fuse the cell membrane with the virus envelope. It is also the primary element of the host's immune system to recognize the virus. In other words, this S protein, which has a glycoprotein structure on the viral cell surface, is an important structural protein in the attachment and entry of the virus into the host cell, and also plays a role in host selection and tissue tropism. It is known that the genetic variation of S proteins has an effect on the virulence of coronaviruses and is also the main target for neutralizing antibodies and anti-viral peptides.

The envelope structure also contains Integral Membrane Glycoproteins (M) as a third type. These glycoproteins are just one of the building proteins on the envelope. M Glycoproteins provide the unique shape of Coronaviruses. Due to their many properties, M Glycoproteins are thought to play a role in the assembly of virus particles after biosynthesis. Because M Glycoproteins are linked to the nucleocapsid in vitro. If M Glycoproteins are sent into the cell alone, they are seen in the Golgi complex in the regions where the virus particles are localized. However, recent studies have shown that the location of the M Glycoproteins is slightly further away from the shadow.

As a result; the S, M and N proteins, known as structural proteins in the host cell, are placed in the Golgi space through the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and combined with RNA and other auxiliary proteins, the complex genetic material passing through the Golgi apparatus, to form the new SARS-CoV. It is known that structural proteins and Orf7a and Orf7b helper proteins work together in the assembly of virion. Thus, the virus formed in the host cell is released from the host through exocytosis and causes infections.

SARS-CoV has a fairly large genome and is about 30 kb in length. The genome is known to have 14 functional open reading frames (ORFs). While ORF 1a and 1b encode replicase and structural proteins, ORF 3a, 3b, 6, 7a, 7b, 8a, 8b and 9b regions among the structural genes encode non-homologous accessory proteins. The other 4 regions are; it encodes the major structural proteins known as S in ORF 2, E in ORF 4, M in ORF 5, and N in ORF 9. In addition, there are 16 NSP (non-structural proteins; nsp1-16) proteins in the ORF 1 region.

Genome sequence map of SARS-CoV

(Gray boxes indicate 3CL protease (3CLpro), polymerase (pol), spike (S), envelope (E), membrane (M) and nucleocapsid (N) genes.)

The sequences of most of these genes are conserved between different species / individuals and it is known that the amino acid sequences of accessory proteins expressed from these genes do not have a significant similarity between viral or cellular proteins.

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About New Type Coronavirus COVID-19:

2019-nCoV is a new enveloped beta-coronavirus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome. A coronavirus consists of four structural proteins: nucleocapsid, envelope, membrane, and rod-like protrusions (spines). Since these protrusions are called "corona", which means crown in Latin, these viruses are called coronavirus (crowned virus). The nucleocapsid contains the genetic material in a sphere-like structure formed by the envelope and membrane proteins. The spiny protrusions identify the cells that the virus can infect and attach to the receptors in the cells.

COVID-19, which belongs to the Nidovirales family, Coronaviridae family, Coronavirinae subfamily and Coronavirus genus, has an enveloped (helical nucleocapsid), 100-130 nm diameter, linear, positive sensitive and single-stranded RNA and its genome size is 29,727 nucleotides.

Coronaviruses typically have a narrow host range and can cause serious illness in many animals; infectious bronchitis virus, feline infectious peritonitis virus and infectious gastroenteritis virus are the most important pathogenic viruses among them. These viruses are also transmitted from animals to humans and cause serious diseases.

SARS-CoV binds to CEACAM1 receptors, known as an adhesion molecule present on the cell surface and found in various tissues such as epithelial cells, leukocytes and tumor cells in humans and animals, and the genome of the virus enters the host cell.

COVID-19's Appearance Under the Microscope; It is a false color scanning electron microscope image showing the COVID-19 virus from a patient in the USA; The viral particles are yellow in color as they emerge from the surface of a blue and pink colored cell.

COVID-19, as well as most coronaviruses such as SARS and MERS, look similar from the outside and have a lump-covered spherical appearance.

SARS-CoV-2 has the typical coronavirus structure with spike protein and also expresses other proteins such as RNA polymerase, 3 chymotrypsin-like protease, papain-like protease, helicase, glycoprotein, and helper proteins. The spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 contains a 3-dimensional structure in the RBD region to maintain van der Waals forces.

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This image was recorded with a transmission electron microscope.

It has a crown-like appearance under an electron microscope. Rocky Mountains Labs researcher Emmie de Wit provided the virus, and microscopist Elizabeth Fischer produced the images and the visual medical arts office colored the images.

For the whole set on Flickr;

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/niaid/albums/72157712914621487/with/49531042877/>

The 394 glutamine residues in the RBD region of SARS-CoV-2 are recognized by the critical lysine 31 residue on the human ACE2 receptor. Structural proteins are encoded by four structural genes, including spike (S), envelope (E), membrane (M) and nucleocapsid (N) genes. Orf1ab is the largest gene in SARS-CoV-2, encoding the pp1ab protein and 15 nsps. The orf1a gene also encodes the pp1a protein, which contains 10 nsps. According to the evolution tree, SARS-CoV-2 is close to the SARS-coronavirus group. Recent studies have shown notable differences, such as the absence of 8a protein in SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2, and fluctuation in the number of amino acids in the 8b and 3c protein in SARS-CoV-2. It is reported that the Spike glycoprotein of Wuhan coronavirus entry into the host cell previously used by SARS-CoV is also reported. The single N501T mutation in the Spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 may have significantly increased its **binding affinity to ACE2**.

The biggest obstacle to research progress:

Animal models play a vital role in designing therapeutic strategies from the introduction of viral pathogenicity mechanisms into transmission. Various animal models showing signs of severe infection have previously been used to study SARS-CoV replication. Unlike SARS-CoV, no pathogenesis of MERS-CoV has been observed in small animals. Mice are not vulnerable to MERS-coronavirus infection due to the DPP4 receptor mismatch. Since the entire genome of the 2019-novel coronavirus is more than %80 similar to the previous human SARS-like bat CoV, animal models previously used for SARS-CoV can be used to study the infectious pathogenicity of SARS-CoV-2. The human ACE2 cell receptor is recognized by both SARS and Novel coronaviruses. As a result, TALEN or CRISPR mediated genetically modified hamsters or other small animals can be used to study the pathogenicity of novel coronaviruses. SARS-CoV has been reported to replicate and cause severe disease in Rats (F344), where sequence analysis revealed a mutation in the spike glycoprotein. Thus, developing the spike glycoprotein targeting therapeutics against novel coronaviruses may be another viable option.

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Recently, mouse models and clinical isolates have been used to develop any therapeutic strategy against SARS-CoV-2-induced COVID-19. In a similar study, artificial intelligence prediction was used to investigate the preventive role of the drug against SARS-CoV-2. Patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 have also been used in randomized clinical trials. It is now important for scientists around the world to collaborate on a suitable model for design and investigate in vivo mechanisms associated with SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis.

ACE2 receiver entrance door:

Coronaviruses can be transmitted from person to person **through droplets** that infected people exhale when they breathe, cough or sneeze. A typical surgical mask cannot prevent the passage of viral particles contained in these droplets, but washing hands; Simple measures such as disinfecting frequently touched surfaces and objects and avoiding touching the face, eyes and mouth can greatly reduce the risk of infection. While coronaviruses that cause mild colds primarily infect the upper respiratory tract (nose and throat), coronaviruses that cause more serious diseases infect the lower respiratory tract (lungs) and cause pneumonia. The SARS virus binds to the hype called ACE2 (angiotensin converting enzyme-2) in the cell, and the MERS virus binds to the host called DPP4 (dipeptidyl peptidase-4). Both receptors are found in cells in different parts of the body, primarily lung cells.

Analyzes showed that the coronavirus that causes COVID-19, like SARS, binds to the ACE2 receptor. On the other hand, a human coronavirus called NL63, which is connected to the same virus, causes only upper respiratory tract infection, while SARS and COVID-19 coronaviruses infect the lower respiratory tract. Another interesting point is that the coronavirus does not infect heart cells, although the ACE2 receptor is also densely found in heart cells. Burtram Fielding, a molecular biologist at Western Cape University in South Africa, says he suspects that other receptors are involved in binding the virus to cells.

Another important feature of coronaviruses is that thanks to their helper proteins, the host can escape from the innate immune response. When immune cells detect a pathogen in the body, the immune response begins with the release of proteins called interferon that prevent the pathogen from reproducing, stop the pathogen's protein synthesis and trigger the death of the pathogen. However, the response of the immune system and this whole process can also be harmful for the host, the person infected by the virus. Because the immune response can sometimes be against the healthy cells of the body and lead to autoimmune diseases. This may have to do with how virulent the virus is, in other words, how devastating the virus causes an immune response. Therefore, the immune system's response can also harm the body rather than protect it. Therefore, in a virus epidemic, other health problems of the person also become important.

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	Group A	Group B	Group AB	Group O
Red blood cell type				
Antibodies in plasma	 Anti-A and Anti-B			
Antigens in red blood cell	 A and B antigens	None		

"Meta-analysis of the data collected together showed that blood type A carries a significantly higher risk for COVID-19 than non-A blood groups" the researchers said.

"Blood type 0 had a significantly lower risk of infectious disease compared to non-0 blood groups."

However, the article clearly states that although the results are meaningful, this is not an all or nothing consequence.

According to the study, the normal population in Wuhan has 31 percent type A, 24 percent type B, 9 percent type AB and 34 percent type 0 blood type distribution. The infected, according to their comparison, are distributed as follows: 38 percent type A, 26 percent type B, 10 percent type AB and 25 percent type 0. Similar differences were also observed in Shenzhen. As can be seen, the normal population and the percentages of those with viruses have some differences. However, this does not mean that people with type 0 blood type are immune, and not everyone who gets the virus will be type A.

What are the symptoms of COVID-19:

First symptoms of the disease are usually **high fever** (> 38 C°), **dry cough**, **change in smell or taste**. In addition, feeling of restlessness, tremors, throat burning, muscle pain, pneumonia, diarrhea (%10-20), shortening of breathing depth or difficult breathing are among the most common symptoms.

While radiological findings in the early stages of the disease show normal images, in the subsequent lung X-rays, consolidated areas due to focal interstitial infiltrates are detected (Al-Hazmi, 2016). Leukopenia is observed in patients, while a decrease in lymphocyte count is noted, lactate dehydrogenase, creatine phosphokinase and transaminase levels may increase. In the following periods, in addition to these findings, thrombocytopenia picture develops in most patients, in other words, the number of platelets in the blood may decrease.

The disease may have a subclinical course in some people, as well as in people with weakened immunity, in children and the elderly or in diabetic people. Also, people with complications such as hepatitis are at higher risk for serious complications.

For the diagnosis of SARS-COV, blood samples, nose/throat cultures, stool and sometimes urine or tissue samples tests taken from patients should be studied in laboratories with biosafety level 3 (BSL-3). It is aimed to reproduce viruses in cell culture from samples taken for this purpose and to investigate various viral proteins involved in the life cycle of the virus. PCR tests (RT-PCR) performed with reverse transcriptases specifically targeting the coronaviruses ORF 1b or nucleoprotein gene, antigen tests with monoclonal antibodies or monospecific polyclonal antibody against N protein, and various serological and immunofluorescent tests performed to show polyclonal antibodies with fluorescent dyes are the basic tests used for. Although immunological tests used for diagnostic purposes are less sensitive than RTPCR, they are known as very sensitive and specific tests in both methods. The biggest disadvantage of immunofluorescence antibody (IFA) tests is that they may give false results at the initial stage of the disease. However, these tests are still used as screening tests that give very effective and rapid results, especially after the 5th day of infection.

Coronavirus can cause a variety of symptoms in different animals. Some strains can cause diarrhea in pigs and turkeys, often causing mild to moderate respiratory infections such as runny nose and sore throat. Some people become infected but do not develop any symptoms. Usually the symptoms are mild, especially in children and young adults. About 1 out of 5 people with coronavirus become seriously ill and have breathing difficulties that require hospitalization. The main symptoms reported in hospital admissions are:

- Fever (more than %80 of patients)
- Cough (> %80)
- Shortness of breath (%31)
- Muscular pain (%11)

Disease; early symptoms such as shortness of breath, difficulty in breathing, increased respiratory secretions (saliva, bloody sputum), increased gastrointestinal symptoms (nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, etc.) or low fever without consciousness changes (confusion, lethargy), cough, weakness can also present with mild symptoms such as discharge.

Limited data on this subject indicate that the mortality rate in hospitalized patients is %11. Complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS, %17), acute kidney injury, acute lung injury, septic shock and ventilator-associated pneumonia are seen in %33 of patients.

Although the elderly or those with more than one disease are thought to be at higher risk, the risk factors for disease progression are still uncertain. In many advanced cases, infections can lead to pneumonia, severe acute respiratory failure, renal failure and death.

How long does the incubation take:

The incubation period represents the time between infection and the development of clinical symptoms. It is currently estimated to range from 2 to 11 days up to a maximum of 14 days. **But this time, when the incubation period is shortened even more with the latest research. Moreover, it turned out that the virus is much more deadly.**

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Elderly people and patients with underlying conditions such as hypertension, heart problems or diabetes, and patients with immunosuppressed are more likely to develop severe forms of the disease. Men are more likely to die from an infection than women because they likely produce weaker immune responses and have higher tobacco consumption, Type 2 diabetes and high blood pressure than women, which can increase the risk of complications following an infection.

They concluded that this new coronavirus can stay on surfaces such as metal, glass and plastic for up to 9 days if it resembles other coronaviruses. (For comparison, flu viruses can survive for a maximum of 48 hours on a surface.) However, some cannot remain active at temperatures above 30 degrees Celsius.

Researchers, who examined previous studies on viruses affecting humans and animals, found in 22 studies that microorganisms that cause disease in humans can survive up to 9 days on many surfaces at room temperature. Researchers say that viruses belonging to the coronavirus family can survive on different materials such as aluminum, wood, paper, plastic and glass for a maximum of 4 to 5 days. Doctor Günter Kampf from Greifswald University Hospital says that low temperature and high humidity increase the lifespan of these viruses.

In a study conducted in England, it was determined that the brains of those who got coronavirus were aged for about 10 years and their IQ decreased. According to the news in the Daily Mirror, in the study conducted by scientists from Imperial College London, Cambridge University, King's College London and the University of Chicago, the damage caused by the coronavirus in the brain was examined. Director of the research, Dr. Adam Hampshire stated that some of the patients who defeated COVID-19 observed that their brains were aged 10 years and that some of them had IQ levels decreased. As a result of the study, it was stated that "individuals with COVID-19 perform worse than expected in cognitive tests in more than one area, considering their detailed age and demographic profiles. The decline in brain health is proportional to how severe the disease is."

How is COVID-19 transmitted:

- Often close human contact (approximately 1.8 meters).
- Human-to-human transmission: Through droplets formed as a result of coughing or sneezing from an infected person, as in flu and other respiratory diseases.
- Spilled droplets can reach the mouth, nose or eyes of other people nearby.
- Although not certain, a person touching their mouth, nose or eyes after touching a surface or inanimate object with SARS-CoV-2.
- The contagiousness of respiratory-transmitted viruses is usually greatest during the period when symptoms are at their peak. In the SARS-CoV-2 virus, a number of cases have been reported regarding transmission in people who have close contact with asymptomatic patients.

It was emphasized by the US Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) that transmission through the **eye** is possible, albeit with a low probability, but the main route of transmission is the respiratory system. It has been shown by scientific studies that the contamination can be a matter of moving hands to the face and eyes of a road that comes into contact with an infected surface. It should be known that eye rash may be one of the symptoms of COVID-19. In addition, another study showed that an increase in tears and burrs may also be symptoms. In a study published in Hubei province of China, where the virus originated, it was stated that the first symptom of only one patient was inflammation of the conjunctiva (conjunctivitis), the membrane that covers the inside of the eyelids and the white area of the eyes.

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In another study conducted on 18 COVID-19 patients at RWTH Aachen University, coronavirus RNA was detected in the tears of 5 (28 percent) of the patients by PCR test. In addition, in the SERPICO-19 study conducted in Milan, it was concluded that COVID-19 could also affect the retina. It has been stated that most of the retinal involvement is caused by the vascular system of the retina. For this reason, the tears or tears of sick people should not be touched.

What is the difference between COVID-19 and the flu:

The first symptoms of COVID-19 and influenza (flu) infections are usually very similar. Both cause fever and similar respiratory symptoms, which can range from mild to severe illness later on and can sometimes be fatal. Both viruses are also transmitted by coughing or sneezing or by contact with hands, surfaces or objects contaminated with the virus. As a result, the same public health measures such as hand hygiene (hand washing), good respiratory etiquette (coughing and disposing of the tissue to your elbow or a tissue immediately), and good house cleaning are important actions to prevent both infections.

The rate of infection is an important difference between the two viruses. Influenza typically has a shorter incubation period (time from infection to symptoms) than COVID-19. This means influenza can spread faster than COVID-19.

COVID-19 treatment:

A drug or vaccine for SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) has not yet been fully developed. Currently, treatment is symptomatic and based on supportive care according to the clinical condition of the patient. Supportive therapy includes oxygen therapy, keeping the patient hydrated, fever and pain management, and antibiotic therapy in case of an additional bacterial infection.

In the treatment of SARS-CoV, corticosteroids, known as an immune modulator treatment method that affect the whole body and have a very strong effect and have anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects, provide early recovery of fever and less harmful radiographic leaks. Ribavirin, which is a nucleoside analogue used in treatment, is known as the most commonly used agent with antiviral activity against many DNA and RNA viruses. Ribavirin blocks the viral replicase polyprotein and stops RNA replication. Another method used in the treatment of SARS-CoV is a protease inhibitor.

Lopinavir-ritonavir co-formulation, which is also used in the treatment of HIV infection, can be used together with ribavirin in the early stages of the disease to aid antiviral therapy. However, additional research is needed to develop new therapies such as additional antiviral therapies, RNA silencing methods, anti-monoclonal antibodies, anti-viral peptides and vaccines, as well as the use of interferon and general steroids in the treatment of immune-mediated lung injuries.

Studies on SARSCoV and MERS-CoV show that the SARS-CoV-2 virus is sensitive to ultraviolet light (UV) and high temperature (30 minutes, 56 °C). In addition, %75 ethanol, chlorine-containing disinfectants, peracetic acid and chloroform effectively inactivate the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Chlorhexidine was not found to be very effective in deactivation of SARS-CoV-2.

Conclusion:

By sequencing the entire genome of COVID-19, it has been possible to extract fast and accurate diagnostic tools and methods. As a result of the detection of viral proteins, the agent can be identified much more quickly. Although its genome is known, there are many gaps such as physical stability and transmissible molecular bases of the virus, molecular and immunological basis of disease pathogenesis in humans, screening tests for early or cryptic SARS cases, and infection controls. An effective treatment method and acceleration of vaccination studies are of great importance. However, the emergence of SARS and other new viruses and the need for such preparation should never be overlooked...

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